

MSc. DATA SCIENCE DISSERTATION

AN OPEN DATASET ARCHITECTURE PROTOTYPE TO DRIVE INNOVATIVE DATA-DRIVEN DECISION-MAKING IN UGANDA'S TERTIARY EDUCATION SECTOR: A CASE OF UICT

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Abstract

This study developed, implemented, and validated a prototype open dataset architecture to promote innovative data-driven decision-making (DDDM) in Uganda's tertiary education sector, with the Uganda Institute of Information and Communications Technology (UICT) serving as a case study. Despite increased investments in digital transformation initiatives and educational information systems, institutional challenges such as fragmented data systems, limited interoperability, weak analytics integration, and underutilization of institutional datasets remain unresolved. Following the Design Science Research (DSR) methodology, the study used a mixed-methods approach that included assessments of institutional requirements, platform prototyping, implementation, and validation. Data were gathered through baseline and post-implementation surveys, stakeholder interviews, document analysis, User Acceptance Testing (UAT), and validation workshops. Quantitative analysis used descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation analysis, whilst qualitative responses were examined thematically. The findings found that UICT's data ecosystem was extremely fragmented among systems such as ACMIS, LMS, HRMIS, and finance platforms, resulting in inconsistent accessibility, limited data integration, and event-driven rather than continuous data utilization for institutional decision-making. The prototype had metadata-driven dataset management, role-based access controls, analytics dashboards, advanced search and filtering tools, export capabilities, and a secure, modular architecture coupled with Power BI and Python Dash analytics tools. Usability testing revealed good platform performance, with a System Usability Scale (SUS) score of 78.4, exceeding the industry norm of 68. This was accompanied by high job completion rates and positive stakeholder views of accessibility, analytics capabilities, and workflow alignment. Although statistical testing revealed no significant relationship between perceived platform impact and data-driven decision-making frequency during the pilot period, qualitative findings indicated significant practical benefits, including improvements in institutional analytics capacity, strategic planning, evidence-based governance, and innovation. The study indicates that the proposed architecture offers a scalable, context-responsive framework to improve digital transformation and data-driven governance in Ugandan higher education institutions and other low-resource settings.

Keywords: data-driven decision-making, open dataset architecture, digital transformation, higher education analytics, institutional data governance.

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

In today's increasingly digital world, data has become a critical asset for improving institutional effectiveness, driving innovation, and informing policy-making—especially within the education sector (Baig et al., 2020; Fischer et al., 2020; Nda et al., 2019). Globally, tertiary institutions are adopting integrated data ecosystems that support decision-making through analytics and visualization tools ('Big Data Visualization and Visual Analytics', 2024; Matto, 2022). In Uganda, institutions such as the Uganda Institute of Information and Communications Technology (UICT) generate large volumes of administrative, academic, and operational data through systems such as the Academic Management Information System (ACMIS), Learning Management Systems (LMS), Human Resource Management Information System (HRMIS), and financial platforms (Salbiah & Muhammad, 2024; Zhang et al., 2022) (Digital Transformation Roadmap, 2024). However, these systems often function in isolation, leading to fragmented data silos, limited interoperability, and minimal use of data for strategic planning and governance.

Despite Uganda's national policies—such as the Digital Uganda Vision and the Digital Transformation Roadmap (2023/24–2027/28)—which highlight the importance of data-driven governance and open data adoption, institutional-level implementation remains limited (Almuqrin et al., 2022; *Digital Transformation / Ministry of ICT and National Guidance*, 2023; Gao et al., 2023). The potential of data to support to support institutional accountability, resource optimization, and strategic planning is constrained by the lack of a unified open dataset framework (Brand et al., 2023; Tropp et al., 2022). This study aims to address these gaps by designing a customized open dataset architecture for UICT that promotes data accessibility, usability, and visualization, thus supporting informed decision-making and innovation.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Although making data-driven decisions is increasingly critical in tertiary education as evidenced by the different information systems like ACMIS, LMS, Chatbots, Social Media platforms, etc that continuously collect and generate data, institutions like UICT in Uganda

face persistent challenges of fragmented data systems, poor interoperability, and underutilized analytics. Existing global models for open dataset architectures are often designed for digitally mature contexts, limiting their applicability in low-resource settings (Vlasenko et al., 2020; Yu et al., 2025). UICT's current siloed systems and inadequate data handling at the different stages of the data lifecycle hinder effective planning, innovation, and evidence-based governance, despite national policies promoting digital transformation. A localized, scalable, and analytics-integrated open dataset platform that addresses UICT's specific operational realities, but is adaptable by other institutions of higher learning. Without such a platform, UICT and similar higher educational institutions risk falling behind in leveraging data for institutional growth, transparency, and strategic decision-making. In an effort to address this gap, this study will assess the existing data management institutional practices then design and evaluate a context-specific open education data prototype architecture that fosters system interoperability, data accessibility, analytics, visualization, and informed decision-making aligned with Uganda's national digital transformation and data strategy goals.

1.3 Research Motivation

The primary motivation for this study stems from both practical issues and strategic opportunities observed within Uganda's tertiary education system. Although much investment has been allocated to the digitalization of academic and administrative processes, many tertiary education institutions in Uganda often lack the requisite digital tools and frameworks necessary to transform existing raw data into actionable insights for decision-making. Like many other tertiary education Institutions, it lacks a centralized, analytics-ready open data platform, which grossly restricts the institution's capabilities to conduct evidence-based planning, analyze trends, and optimize resource allocation. It is therefore critical to bridge the existing gap between data collected and its practical use for innovation and decision-making. Additionally, the study supports Uganda's national priority areas of improving educational outcomes and promoting digital transformation by using open, secure, and interoperable data systems (*Digital Transformation / Ministry of ICT and National Guidance, 2023*). The researcher's motivation is to develop a scalable, context-responsive platform that can meet the strategic and operational needs of UICT while promoting broader national goals within the Digital Transformation Programme of the National Development Plan IV (2026-2030).

1.4 Purpose of the Study

This study's primary goal is to develop and evaluate a prototype open dataset architecture suited to UICT's institutional requirements. The platform will include data analytics and visualization tools, anonymized institutional datasets, and other key functionalities to enable and facilitate practical data usage to inform operational and strategic decision-making across departments. By doing so, the researcher hopes to enhance data governance and stimulate innovation in UICT's decision-making processes, while offering a model that can be tailored for use in other Ugandan tertiary education institutions.

1.5 Specific objectives

1. To assess the current data management and decision-making practices at UICT, and to identify key data requirements essential for supporting data-driven decision-making within UICT.
2. To design a prototype open dataset platform architecture that addresses UICT's identified data needs, incorporating analytics and visualization tools to support data-driven decision-making.
3. To implement, Test, and validate a prototype platform to support data-driven decision-making at UICT.

1.6 Research Questions

To guide the study, the following research questions are posed:

1. How is data currently managed and used at UICT, and what challenges and gaps affect data-driven decision-making?
2. What system features and architectural components are required to design an effective open dataset platform for UICT?
3. How effective, usable, and impactful is the proposed platform in supporting innovation and decision-making at UICT?

1.7 Research Hypothesis

Given the scope of this study, the following hypothesis corresponding to each specific objective above has been considered:

1. **H1** : There is no significant association between perceived data quality (accuracy, timeliness, completeness) and staff confidence in making data-driven decisions.
2. **H2** : There is no significant association between staff preference for specific analytics tools and their perceived usefulness of the proposed platform
3. **H3** : The proposed platform has no statistically significant perceived impact on data-driven decision-making

1.8 Significance of the Study

From an academic, policy, and practical perspective, this study is critical in that it strengthens institutional capacity for data-driven governance by having UICT develop a working prototype of an open dataset architecture. Policy-wise, the study offers insights that align with Uganda's digital transformation goals by promoting the adoption of open, interoperable educational data systems (NPA, 2020). Additionally, the study fills a practical and theoretical gap by demonstrating how open data systems can be localized to meet governance and decision-making needs within tertiary institutions in sub-Saharan Africa (Adeniran et al., 2024; Rasool et al., 2022). Additionally, by offering helpful recommendations for policymakers, educational managers, developers, and data scientists who wish to improve institutional decision-making and innovation, the study contributes to the discourse on educational data system design in low-resource contexts.

1.9 Delimitations, Limitations, and Assumptions

The study is delimited to the UICT and focuses on data management systems within a single institution. The research is restricted to datasets relevant to UICT's internal operations and decision-making. Limitations include possible restricted access to sensitive datasets, resource constraints that may limit full deployment of the system within the dissertation timeframe, and the limited generalizability of findings beyond UICT. Key assumptions include the availability

of stakeholder participation, institutional willingness to engage in system design and testing, and the presence of baseline digital infrastructure to implement and test the prototype.

1.11 Outline of the Report

This dissertation is segmented into six (6) primary chapters: Chapter One introduces the study, providing the background, research motivation, purpose, research questions, significance, key definitions, and scope. Chapter Two 'digs' comprehensively into existing and relevant literature, discussing theoretical frameworks, global and local perspectives, data management practices in tertiary educational institutions, design of open dataset architecture, analytics and decision support, etc. Chapter Three details the methodology, describing the research design, sampling strategy, data collection methods, analysis techniques, and system design approaches. Chapter four presents the findings, evaluation results of the prototype, and an interpretation of stakeholder feedback. Chapter five discusses the findings about existing literature, implications for policy, and providing recommendations for institutional application. Chapter six concludes the study by summarizing key findings and providing recommendations for future research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter offers an essential summary of literature on data governance in higher education, open education data and the development of the open education portal to facilitate data-driven decision making and innovation. This chapter explains the theoretical underpinnings and practical data-driven decision-making challenges faced by Uganda, tertiary educational institutions and is thematically structured to capture both local and global contexts. To promote the development of a scalable, analytics-enabled, open dataset architecture, that is suitable for its institutional environment, particular focus was given to the Uganda Institute of Information and Communications Technology as a case study.

2.2 Theoretical Foundations

The foundation of this study is built on three interrelated theoretical lenses: Data-Driven Decision-Making (DDDM) Theory, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), and Open Systems Theory. Each offers a unique perspective on how institutions can transform raw data into actionable insights. According to DDDM theory, effective and efficient decision-making relies on the ability of institutions to systematically collect, analyse, and optimally utilize data to provide academic interventions, allocate available resources, and inform policy formulation (Gul et al., 2023; Mandinach & Gummer, 2016). It offers a compelling case for developing data systems that are comparable to the one being recommended in this study and accentuates accountability, efficiency and transparency in institutional operations. The benefits of DDM are however limited by empirical evidence indicating that institutions in environments with limited resources suffer from inconsistent practices regarding data and underdeveloped governance structures (Asfaw et al., 2023, 2023).

Davis (1989) developed a Technology acceptance model (TAM) that is essential for assessing the possibility of the open education data portal platform being adopted based on the degree to which a user believes that using a given system will enhance their job performance, while the system is easy to use the system i.e., perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. TAM is therefore essential in assessing the usability and stakeholder readiness for the open dataset platform at UICT. This is because user acceptance testing (UAT) is a critical component of any technical system's success.

The dynamic interplay between tertiary education institutions and their environment is highlighted by *Katz, D., & Kahn, R. L. (1978)*, which views institutions as systems that accept inputs from the environment and process them to produce outputs that are fed back into the system. In the case of the open education data portal, education datasets from other systems hosted within or outside UICT will act as inputs, followed by data processing to ensure curated, anonymized datasets that allow for integration, analysis, and visualization with the portal. Usable open datasets with interactive dashboards will be available to different users to download for further analysis or derive insights from existing visualizations to inform policymakers, researchers, and educators. The platform is provisioned with feedback loops to inform further improvements. The operating environment for the open education data portal comprises of internal stakeholders, including staff and faculty, as well as external stakeholders like other tertiary institutions, ministries, researchers, NGOs, and international agencies.

2.3 Open Data in Education: Global and Local Perspectives

The research literature continually underscores how open data is a transformative enabler in the education sector through the promotion of innovation, transparency, and informed decision-making (Alsaad, 2023; Bachtiar & Muhamad, 2020; Rasool et al., 2022). Internationally, open education data has indicated potential for improving accountability, resource allocation optimization, and fostering cross-institutional research collaboration (Adeniran et al., 2024; Atz et al., 2015; Salubi, 2025). Even though these benefits are well-documented in developed economies like Uganda, the practical implementation of open data systems in developing nations has been uneven. According to research by Pangaribuan (2019) and *UNESCO* (2021), in resource-constrained environments, infrastructure limitations with siloed systems, inadequate stakeholder capabilities, and weak data governance frameworks within institutions continue to be significant obstacles. Most international initiatives like in UK and USA prioritize national-level open data platforms which are useful for policy-making and transparency at macro-level. and US. While effective for macro-level transparency and policy benchmarking but frequently ignore the specific decision-making requirements of individual institutions (Davies, 2014; Kassen, 2013; Rodriguez et al., 2020). As such, they are usually ill-

prepared to support institutions or universities particularly those in developing and 3rd world countries. In Uganda, where tertiary institutions encounter compounded challenges including fragmented systems, inadequate analytics capacity, and a lack of integrated platforms suited to local realities context, the gap between macrolevel and micro-level utilization is very pronounced. Despite the considerable theoretical promise of open education data, there are few institutional-level models capable of contextual adaptation. Even when open data is being hailed globally for improving educational accountability and democratizing access (Atz et al., 2015; Rasool et al., 2022), Uganda's tertiary institutions remain under-equipped to leverage these benefits.

2.4 Data Management in Higher Education Institutions

A growing number of research investigations have examined data management practices in tertiary education institutions, finding that tools for collecting data and structures for institutional reporting have improved significantly. The works of Contreras et al. (2024), Mohammed & Ibrahim (2019), and Mutanov et al. (2020) are all essential contributions to this discussion. Together, they acknowledge advancements that have been made in these areas.

The adoption of systems like Academic Management Information Systems (ACMIS) has contributed to digitisation with better structured reporting processes. However, more in-depth analyses, such as those by Ariko (2024), Jakimoski (2016), and Kostoska et al. (2014), reveal that these improvements are less effective due to persistent systemic issues. Interoperability issues between systems, the presence of data silos, and the lack of real-time access to integrated data for institutional decision-makers are some of the critical challenges. These structural deficiencies restrict the sharing of information and hinder institutions from performing timely and informed decision-making. Existing data systems are of less strategic significance due to the absence of built-in analytics or real-time dashboards. This is especially true for performance tracking and policy implementation.

Most of the recent past research has focused on how to technically deploy data systems. However, there is evident lack of research on how to functionally integrate these systems into decision-making frameworks. Ariko (2024) and Mutanov et al. (2020) argue that without harmonized governance protocols and interoperable designs, even systems that are technologically very advanced may not be able to produce actionable insights.

As a result, there is a consensus that educational institutions and universities—especially those with limited resources—need open dataset architectures that go beyond just data storage but also support unified access, analytics, and visualisation. To ensure data management practices are in line with institutional goals and national policy frameworks, such systems must be designed with strategic foresight.

2.5 Open Dataset Architecture Design: From Global Models to Local Applicability

There is a range of models in the existing literature on dataset architecture design that advocate for modularity, interoperability, compliance with standards, and secure data access mechanisms. Liu et al. (2022) and Orr & Crawford (2024) are two examples of scholars whose frameworks suggest that metadata integration, application programming interfaces (APIs), and privacy-enhancing mechanisms are critical components for building robust open data systems. These architectural models have been praised for their alignment with global best practices in system design and data management (Fernandez et al., 2023; Loechel et al., 2024; Sowmya et al., 2023).

However, a critical limitation in this body of work is assuming that there is already well-developed digital infrastructure, mature data governance ecosystems, and highly skilled personnel, as in developed countries. Most of these studies are based on national-level implementations or technologically advanced academic environments, which undermines their transferability to institutions with limited resources (Kassen, 2013). In places with low incomes, like Uganda, and more specifically at the Uganda Institute of Information and Communications Technology (UICT), the adoption of these advanced architectures is further hindered by limited funding, data management capabilities among staff, low internet bandwidth, and fragmented systems.

2.6 Embedded Analytics and Decision Support

Having competencies in utilizing data management, analytics, and visualisation tools can be critical enablers for enhancing better data-driven decision-making in the education sector, particularly, tertiary education. Bhargava et al. (2018), Chen et al. (2012), and Murumba (2019) all write a lot about tools like Power BI, Tableau, and Python-based dashboards because they can help with institutional planning, performance monitoring, and communication with stakeholders through easy-to-use, visual interfaces. These tools help organisations make better

decisions by transforming raw data into actionable insights, thereby fostering timely and informed decisions.

There is a notable lack of literature that critically examines the systematic integration of these tools into open dataset architectures, particularly in tertiary educational contexts, despite their widespread use in higher education globally. Most of the available literature discusses data analytics as standalone applications instead of as embedded components of larger data platforms. Because of this, there isn't much empirical evidence on how to use real-time analytics in data-sharing systems that are specific to education.

2.7 Innovation and Data-Informed Decision-Making in Uganda

Uganda's policy frameworks, such as the Digital Transformation Roadmap (2023/24–2027/28) and the Third National Development Plan III/IV, stress the critical role of data and digital infrastructure in transforming public service delivery including education (Ministry of ICT & National Guidance, 2023). These national strategies set high goals for integrating data-driven approaches in institutional planning, innovation, and service optimisation. Nevertheless, even though these policy interventions were meant to do good things, their implementation at the institutional level has been very slow and fragmented. It can be argued that this disconnect is caused by institutions not having adequate resources, insufficient digital infrastructure, and not having context-specific tools necessary to operationalize national frameworks. Whereas such policies promote the use of data for innovation, many tertiary institutions and universities, including UICT, continue to operate within traditional data ecosystems where data is collected passively, with minimal interoperability, and siloed systems. There is a gap between what national policy wants to do and what institutions can do. Available data is still being underutilized for real-time decision-making and creating sustainable innovations.

The literature further highlights that Uganda's tertiary institutions lack localised models and frameworks to operationalize policy and through datasets that are easy to access and interpret (Jjagwe et al., 2024; Mutatina et al., 2017). Although existing frameworks recognize the importance of data analytics and visualisation, few studies give empirical examples or tested systems that demonstrate how tertiary education institutions can transform available data into actionable insights for decision-making. This gap suggests that the national goal for digital transformation in education will remain partially fulfilled unless there is a tailored, scalable open data platform that fits within the needs of each institution.

2.8 Identified Gaps and Justification for the Study

Despite the growing focus on open data and data-driven innovation in education around the world, a close look at the existing literature shows that there are significant gaps, especially in the context of tertiary education institutions in developing countries like Uganda. While prior research has advanced foundational concepts in open data principles, educational data systems, and the use of data analytics (Atz et al., 2015; Rasool et al., 2022), these studies are often either too theoretical or too generalised, and lack practical and localized implementation.

Most importantly, few real-world studies adopt a full-cycle approach, which involves examining institutional data practices, designing custom dataset architectures, and evaluating their usability, effectiveness, and impact on institutional innovation and decision-making. Most existing models assume that institutions like UICT already have robust technical infrastructure and data governance structures, which do not reflect operational realities within these institutions. Because of this, their applicability in low-resource contexts is limited, hence leaving a significant knowledge and implementation gap.

Furthermore, the reviewed literature consistently reveals three specific problems. First, there is a scarcity of open dataset architectures that can be adapted to institution-specific environments under low-resource settings. Second, even when platforms are suggested, they often lack integrated analytics and visualization tools necessary for generating actionable insights. Third, there are few studies evaluating these platforms in real-world institutional settings, particularly in terms of usability, stakeholder adoption, and decision-making impact in Uganda's tertiary education sector.

2.9 Conclusion

In conclusion, this chapter has critically reviewed the theoretical, technical, and practical literature related to the development of an open dataset architecture in the tertiary education sector. While global frameworks offer valuable insights, their relevance to Uganda's institutional context requires adaptation. The literature strongly supports the development of a localized, analytics-enabled open dataset platform to address UICT's operational and strategic data needs. This study, therefore, responds to a clearly defined gap by proposing a tailored solution that bridges theory and practice in the context of data-driven innovation in Uganda's

tertiary education sector. The literature review indicated that there are many theoretical contributions to open data frameworks, analytics integration, and system architecture. But in Uganda's higher education, practical use remains nascent and fragmented. The current study fills a critical gap by contextualizing and designing a tailored open dataset architecture that bridges theory and practice for institutional innovation and data-driven decision-making.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

The chapter outlines the methodological framework used to develop, implement, and validate a prototype open dataset platform aimed at promoting innovation and data-driven decision-making (DDDM) at the UICT. To address the three research objectives, the study combines quantitative and qualitative methods guided by the Design Science Research (DSR) methodology:

1. To assess the current data management and decision-making practices at UICT, and to identify key data requirements essential for supporting data-driven decision-making within UICT.
2. To design a prototype open dataset platform that addresses UICT's identified data needs, incorporating analytics and visualization tools to support data-driven decision-making.
3. To implement, Test, and validate a prototype platform to support data-driven decision-making at UICT.

The chapter describes the research design, sampling technique, and data collection techniques employed during the requirements gathering, needs assessment, and pilot testing stages. Additionally, it represents the steps involved in system design and prototyping, stakeholder validation, hypothesis testing, and usability testing. Techniques for both quantitative and qualitative analysis are described, followed by ethical considerations.

3.2 Research Design

The study used a Design Science Research (DSR) methodology with workflow process in Figure 3.1, which is ideal for developing and evaluating technological artefacts that tackle real-world problems (Hevner et al., 2004). Its iterative process ensured that the open dataset platform was both conceptually sound and operationally relevant by fusing theory with practical design. The research progressed through three linked stages:

Phase I: Institutional Assessment, involves conducting a needs assessment that identifies current practices, obstacles, and priorities through stakeholder workshops, baseline and post-

implementation surveys (SQ1, SQ2), and document reviews; Phase II: System design and prototyping, including the development of architecture, specifications, analytics integration (Power BI, Python Dash), and governance features like role-based access etc; and Phase III: Implementation, Testing, and Validation, which includes conducting stakeholder validation workshops, User Acceptance Testing (UAT), and hypothesis testing (H1–H3) after deployment in a semi-production environment. Phase-by-phase iterative feedback guaranteed continuous enhancement, conformity to institutional requirements, and readiness for practical deployment.

Figure 3. 1. Workflow processes

3.3 Sampling Strategy

The study population consisted of UICT staff from the academic, administrative, ICT, and senior management categories. A mixed purposive and stratified sampling strategy ensured depth and breadth of representation. Purposive sampling targeted experts in data management and governance, key informants—including senior management and unit heads from departments like ICT, Research & Innovation, Procurement, Planning, Human Resource, Business Development, and the library—were chosen explicitly through purposeful sampling. To ensure balanced representation across functional units and capture a range of requirements and challenges, stratified sampling guided the distribution of the questionnaire. Fifty-eight (58) respondents participated in Phase I of the SQ1 baseline survey, which evaluated accessibility, DDDM barriers, and current data practices. For design validation, Phase II involved 15 key informants from the fields of ICT, Academic Registry, Finance, and Research & Innovation. Phase III evaluated improvements in data accessibility, analytics, and decision-making by distributing the SQ2 post-implementation survey to 20 pilot participants. This approach ensured a robust baseline and post-deployment insights.

3.4 Data Collection Methods

To collect both quantitative and qualitative data, two structured questionnaires were distributed at different times during the study. During Phase I, the SQ1 Baseline Survey was conducted to assess the institution's current data practices, including quality, accessibility, analytical capacity, and barriers to DDDM. This survey offered a thorough grasp of the baseline, which could be used to gauge future impact of the open education data portal platform. In Phase III, after the prototype platform was deployed, the SQ2 Post-Implementation Survey was conducted. It evaluated how stakeholders perceived improvements in data accessibility, analytical strength, and the degree to which the platform enabled academic, administrative, and strategic decision-making. Both SQ1 and SQ2 combined open-ended items to gather more in-depth qualitative information about user experiences, challenges, and recommendations with closed-ended Likert-scale questions to record measurable metrics. The surveys' mixed-format design made sure that they offered both quantifiable indicators for statistical analysis and comprehensive contextual feedback to guide platform refinement and adoption strategies.

3.5 Platform Architecture Design and Prototyping Procedures

3.5.1 Overview of platform design and prototype development

The prototype platform was developed using the build-evaluate cycle of design science research methodology. Functional requirements included dataset uploads with required metadata tagging, export capabilities, search/filter tools, interactive dashboards, and an integrated feedback system. Scalability, modular architecture, interoperability, and mobile responsiveness were highlighted in non-functional specifications. The development of the platform used Firebase Realtime Database/Firestore for backend storage, Firebase Hosting (SSL encryption), and embedded analytics using Python Dash and Power BI Embedded. To comply with institutional governance requirements, role-based access controls were set up.

Table 3. 1

Platform Requirements

Functional	Non-Functional
Role-based access control functionality	Integration with existing systems (eDoc, LMS, ACMIS)
Dataset upload in standard formats (CSV, XML, JSON)	Modularity (loosely linked components for scalability)
Metadata tagging (Name, Description, Source, Category, Date last Updated, Type, Frequency)	Enhanced security (user authentication, encryption)
Search and filtering	Mobile responsiveness & device accessibility
Interactive dashboards & visualisations	Customisable dashboards
Download functionality	Metadata inclusion with datasets
Feedback mechanism	Clear data lifecycle management protocols (archival & updates)
Usage analytics	

3.5.2 Design diagrams for the platform prototype

Figure 3. 2. Data Flow Diagram

Figure 3. 3. Security Architecture

Figure 3. 4. System Architecture

Figure 3. 5. User Interface Wireframes

3.5.3 Screenshots for the developed platform prototype

Figure 3. 6. Dashboard of Platform Prototype

Dataset Name

Dataset Description

Dataset Category

Data Source

Cover Period

Update Frequency

Usage Information

Upload Your Dataset

Drag and drop files here or [browse](#)

File Type

Excel Mapping

1 Destination Delete

Add Mapping

Submit

Figure 3. 7. Meta data attributes for uploaded datasets

Search datasets

Select Category Select Institution Search

DITB StudentPerformance 2021 Sem1
 Data source: UICT
 Student Performance
 April 1, 2025 at 04:04 PM

CSV XML JSON View Dataset

DEEE Student Performance 2020 Sem1
 Data source: UICT
 Student Performance
 April 1, 2025 at 06:50 PM

CSV XML JSON View Dataset

DITB Student Performance 2019 Sem 1
 Data source: UICT
 Student Performance
 April 1, 2025 at 03:18 PM

CSV XML JSON View Dataset

DEEE Student Performance 2021 Sem1
 Data source: UICT
 Student Performance
 April 1, 2025 at 06:30 PM

CSV XML JSON View Dataset

DEEE Student Performance 2019 Sem1
 Data source: UICT
 Student Performance
 April 1, 2025 at 07:10 PM

CSV XML JSON View Dataset

Figure 3. 8. Uploaded dataset formats

Dataset Records

Id	STUDENT_NO	STUDENT_SEX	STUDENT_PROGRAM	SEMESTER	STUDY_TIME	CU1_CW	CU1_E
166	S0000507	F	DITB	N/A	WEEKEND	31	41
167	S0000516	M	DITB	N/A	WEEKEND	17	35
168	S0000611	F	DITB	N/A	DAY	29	34
169	S0000718	M	DITB	N/A	EVENING	32	37
170	S0000722	M	DITB	N/A	DAY	33	25
171	S0000726	M	DITB	N/A	WEEKEND	34	19
172	S0000727	M	DITB	N/A	DAY	37	57
173	S0000729	M	DITB	N/A	DAY	24	26
174	S0000733	M	DITB	N/A	DAY	17	24
175	S0000735	M	DITB	N/A	DAY	16	47

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Figure 3. 9. Sample of uploaded dataset features

Figure 3. 10. Role-based security access controls

3.6 Testing and Validation Procedures

Stakeholder training engagement, statistical hypothesis analysis, and structured user testing were all used in the prototype platform's testing and validation process to guarantee its institutional relevance and functional soundness. A structured framework with 15 functional test cases spanning all major platform modules was used to conduct User Acceptance Testing (UAT). To ensure usability and functional requirements were met, a task was deemed successful if at least 80% of participants finished it without causing any significant errors. Then, using data from the SQ2 post-implementation survey and system usage logs, hypothesis testing was conducted to assess three predetermined hypotheses (H1–H3) statistically. Finding correlations between variables like data quality, preferred analytics tools, perceived platform usefulness, and perceived impact on data-driven decision-making (DDDM) was the primary goal of the analysis. Following UAT, we conducted a stakeholder validation workshop to synthesize findings from both quantitative and qualitative evaluations, verify the platform's readiness for wider institutional deployment, and gather helpful suggestions to guide full-scale

adoption and upcoming improvements. This multi-pronged validation approach made sure that the platform was in line with institutional workflows, user needs, and strategic priorities, in addition to being technically sound.

3.7 Data Analysis Techniques

To fully interpret the data gathered, the study used both quantitative and qualitative analysis techniques. Descriptive statistics, frequency distributions, mean scores, Pearson correlation, and significance testing at the 5% level ($p < 0.05$) were used for the quantitative analysis to look for patterns and relationships in the data. The study conducted analyses in Python by utilizing libraries for data management, computation, and statistical testing, including Pandas, NumPy, and SciPy. The study employed both quantitative and qualitative analysis techniques to comprehensively interpret the collected data. For the **quantitative analysis**, descriptive statistics, frequency distributions, mean scores, Pearson correlation, and significance testing at the 5% level ($p < 0.05$) were performed to examine relationships and patterns within the data. These analyses were conducted in Python, utilising the Pandas, NumPy, and SciPy libraries for data management, computation, and statistical testing. Transcripts from focused group discussions during stakeholder engagements, as well as open-ended survey responses, were subjected to thematic coding for the qualitative analysis. In this process, recurrent themes pertaining to platform usability, data governance, and institutional adoption were methodically found, categorised, and interpreted. A comprehensive and sophisticated grasp of the platform's functionality, user perspectives, and organisational readiness for adoption was made possible by the integration of both analytical approaches.

3.8 Ethical Considerations

The researcher first obtained Ethical clearance from UICT's Management. All participants provided informed consent. Data collection adhered to Uganda's Data Protection and Privacy Act (2019), ensuring secure storage, encryption of sensitive datasets, and restricted access via role-based permissions. The researcher applied anonymisation and pseudonymization techniques to secondary data files from the ACMIS system, survey, and focused group data to protect participant identities.

3.9 Validity and Reliability

To ensure validity and reliability was critical in guaranteeing credible findings. The study's objectives and pertinent literature on DDDM, open data platforms, and institutional governance were matched with the content of the survey instruments (SQ1, SQ2) and interview/ focused group discussion protocols in order to ensure validity. To guarantee clarity and applicability, instruments were piloted and evaluated by specialists in the Data Science field. By establishing survey questions and test cases in the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Open Systems Theory, which capture key concepts like perceived utility, usability, and institutional readiness, reinforced construct validity. Additionally, by merging data from surveys, stakeholder focus groups, system logs, and document/system analysis, triangulation further enhanced validity. Consistent procedures for gathering data, standardised survey administration, the use of a single, qualified researcher for all focus groups, and UAT sessions to reduce bias all contributed to the preservation of reliability. Quantitative analyses were repeatable using Python scripts for statistical computations, and qualitative data from survey questionnaires were thematically coded using survey monkey software. Lastly, System Test Cases, a structured UAT framework, was used to guarantee consistent performance evaluation. Collectively, these steps taken together ensured that the findings accurately represented the phenomena under study and could guide future research in comparable higher education contexts as well as institutional decision-making.

Chapter 4: Findings

4.1 Introduction

The findings of this study are presented in alignment with its three research objectives, drawing on evidence from baseline and post-implementation surveys (SQ1 and SQ2), key informant stakeholder engagements, document and system analysis, prototype user acceptance testing (UAT), and stakeholder validation workshops.

For **Objective 1**, results examine UICT’s institutional context, data governance practices, and capacity gaps, focusing on workflows, accessibility, quality perceptions, and data use in decision-making.

Objective 2 findings translate institutional needs into technical specifications for the open dataset platform, outlining prioritised functional and non-functional requirements, preferred analytics tools, and the system architecture guiding prototyping.

Objective 3 presents outcomes of implementation, testing, and validation, including deployment environment, usability metrics, hypothesis testing, stakeholder feedback, and the platform’s perceived impact on decision-making and innovation.

4.2 Findings for objective 1: Data Governance and Institutional Needs Assessment

4.2.1 Respondent profile and Institutional context

Two surveys, SQ1 (58 respondents) and SQ2 (17 respondents), captured diverse perspectives on data use at UICT. SQ1 used uniform random sampling across staff, students, and alumni; SQ2 targeted unit heads, ICT staff, and senior management. Respondents were mostly male, aged 35–44, highly educated, experienced, and from varied professional backgrounds, notably information systems and engineering. Insights derived from the two surveys can be represented figures 4.1 – 4.3 below.

Figure 4. 1. Age and gender distribution of SQ1 respondents

Figure 4. 2. Education and professions of SQ1 respondents

Figure 4. 3. Details of the SQ2 sample and role distribution

The demographic insights from SQ1 and SQ2 reveal that the baseline survey (SQ1) captured perspectives from a predominantly male (70.1%) and mid-career (35–44 years, 48.3%) workforce, with a high level of academic qualification—most holding Master’s (58.6%) or Bachelor’s (31%) degrees. The majority were faculty members (48.3%), supported by a significant proportion of administrative/support staff (24.1%), suggesting strong representation from both academic and operational domains. In contrast, SQ2, though smaller in scale (17 participants; 68% response rate), was strategically targeted at unit and department heads, ICT support staff, and senior management, resulting in a balanced representation of decision-makers and technical personnel. Together, these datasets offer a robust institutional profile, ensuring that findings reflect both the strategic priorities of leadership and the operational realities faced by technical and academic staff, thereby strengthening the credibility and applicability of the study’s conclusions.

4.2.2 Current Data Management Practices at UICT

Figure 4. 4. Tools for collecting and processing data

Figure 4. 5. Data types most frequently accessed

The graphics above reveal that UICT’s data management practices rely heavily on basic and widely accessible tools, with Microsoft Excel and Access dominating usage (84.5%), followed by SPSS (53.5%) and limited adoption of advanced platforms such as Power BI (17.2%). This

suggests a strong foundation in basic data handling but limited engagement with more sophisticated analytics tools, potentially constraining deeper institutional insights. Data access patterns indicate a focus on operational and administrative priorities, with staff information (47.1%), student records and performance (41.2%), and financial/procurement data (38.2%) being most accessed. Research projects and innovation data (38.3%) also feature prominently, reflecting some alignment with academic development goals. However, comparatively lower access to LMS logs (35.3%), infrastructure and library data (23.5%), and especially alumni data (11.7%) points to underutilisation of datasets that could support strategic initiatives such as learning analytics, resource planning, and alumni engagement. Collectively, the results suggest a need to expand tool adoption for advanced analytics, enhance integration across data sources, and promote the use of underexploited datasets to strengthen evidence-based decision-making and institutional effectiveness.

4.2.3 Perceived Data Quality and accessibility

The diverging stacked bar chart in Figure 4.6 below shows a mixed perception among respondents regarding the quality and accessibility of institutional data at UICT. While over one-third (35.5%) strongly agreed that the data they use is accurate, a comparable share either disagreed or strongly disagreed, signalling significant variation in confidence.

Figure 4. 6. Stakeholder perspectives on the accessibility and quality of the data

Timeliness and completeness also drew moderate approval but had sizeable proportions of disagreement, indicating delays and gaps in available datasets. Policy clarity scored the lowest, with the majority neutral or in disagreement, suggesting limited awareness or communication of data governance policies. The presence of high neutral responses further hints at possible uncertainty or lack of direct engagement with certain data governance aspects.

Figure 4. 7. Average scores for accessibility and data quality features

The radar chart in Figure 4.7 above reveals that none of the measured attributes scored above 3.18 on a 5-point scale, signalling improvement needs. Data reliability (3.18) and accuracy (3.0) scored highest, indicating general trust but some quality concerns. Completeness (2.83) and timeliness (2.77) ranked lower, pointing to missing data and update delays. Awareness of data protection (2.88) exceeded policy clarity (2.53), showing gaps in governance communication.

Figure 4. 8. Obstacles to accessing data

The Pareto analysis in Figure 4.8 above reveals that lack of access rights (58.8%) is the most significant barrier to data use, contributing the largest share of accessibility issues. Poor data quality (35.3%) and outdated data (29.4%) follow as secondary barriers, but when combined with access restrictions, they account for the majority of challenges faced by staff. This prioritisation underscores the need to first address systemic access control issues, followed by quality assurance and timely updates, to meaningfully improve data-driven decision-making.

In conclusion, the findings from this survey show pressing challenges related to access restrictions, incomplete or outdated data, and unclear institutional policies. Together, these issues constrain effective use of data for decision-making at UICT and highlight the need for targeted improvements in data governance, quality assurance, and Accessibility protocols.

4.2.4 Usage of Data in Decision Making

This bar chart below illustrates the proportion of respondents who indicated that specific decision types at UICT rely on data. The results show that academic decisions (92.3%) are the most data-driven, followed closely by institutional decisions (86.5%) and strategic planning (78%).

Figure 4. 9. Decision types supported by data

The findings highlight the strong reliance on data for operational and academic functions but suggest comparatively lower engagement in strategic, long-term planning, indicating opportunities to strengthen data use in policy development and institutional strategy.

Figure 4. 10. Frequency of data use for decision-making

This bar chart in Figure 4.10 above displays the proportion of respondents indicating how often their departments use data to inform decisions. While 48.1% reported regular use, 38.5% indicated occasional use, and 13.4% reported minimal or no use. These findings reveal significant disparities in data utilization across departments, suggesting that consistent application of data-driven practices remains a challenge despite the availability of institutional datasets. Regarding respondent satisfaction with data analytics for Decision-Making at UICT, satisfaction levels with the use of data analytics in decision-making. Only 34.6% expressed satisfaction, while 26.9% were neutral, and 38.5% expressed dissatisfaction. The dissatisfaction was linked to issues such as poor data quality, restricted real-time access, and lack of automation in reporting. These findings suggest that while analytics are being used, systemic improvements are needed to enhance their effectiveness and user satisfaction.

Figure 4. 11. Event-driven trends in data usage

This bar chart in Figure 4.11 above presents the proportion of respondents who reported increased data usage during specific institutional events. Data is most heavily relied upon during student admissions (88.5%), budget preparation (80.8%), and performance appraisals (65.4%). These results confirm that data use at UICT follows a cyclical, event-driven pattern rather than being a continuous practice, underscoring the need for embedding data-driven decision-making into routine institutional processes.

In general, evidence suggests that data usage in higher educational institutions like UICT has a cyclical pattern and is largely event-driven rather than being an institutional culture embedded in daily routines. Although UICT has made progress in implementing data-driven decision making, findings also highlight variability in practice across departments. To support consistent and timely decision-making, there is room for system improvements that are currently fragmented, staff training in data utilization and management practices, and strong data governance.

4.2.5 Staff Confidence & Capacity in Using Data

This bar chart in Figure 4.12 below shows the adoption of various data analysis tools among UICT staff. Excel dominates at 88.2%, reflecting its familiarity and accessibility.

Figure 4. 12. Adoption of data analysis tools

Python Dashboards (29.4%) and Power BI (11.8%) are far less common, indicating limited uptake of advanced analytics and visualization tools. The heavy reliance on Excel suggests strong basic data-handling capacity but underscores the need for targeted capacity-building to increase adoption of more sophisticated, dynamic, and interactive analytics solutions.

Figure 4. 13. Perceived availability of core data skills

This grouped bar chart in Figure 4.13 above highlights staff perceptions of skill availability for dataset collection, cleaning, analysis, and interpretation. While over half report “available” skills for handling large datasets (53.5%) and data analysis (57.9%), only a small fraction rate these as “very available” (8.6% and 10.5%, respectively). A notable proportion remain unsure, suggesting uneven distribution of competencies across departments. These findings point to moderate institutional readiness but emphasize the importance of structured, institution-wide training in advanced data management to support consistent, organization-wide data-driven decision-making.

Collectively, these findings highlight a positive baseline of staff confidence and data-use skills. Still, they also show gaps in the adoption of advanced tools and specialized skillsets that are necessary for deeper, institution-wide data-driven decision making.

4.2.6 Hypothesis Testing (H1)

To evaluate the correlation between perceived data quality and staff confidence in data-driven decision making, Pearson correlation analysis was conducted by using weighted average scores derived from key indicators in SQ2, such as completeness, timeliness, reliability, and accuracy.

In contrast, staff confidence indicators such as frequency of data use, confidence in data-driven decisions, and frequency of data discussions were extracted using the same survey tool. With a p-value of 0.89, the Pearson correlation coefficient between confidence scores and the perceived data quality ratings was found to be $r = -0.18$. This result indicates that the two variables have a weak negative and statistically insignificant correlation. Thus, the null hypothesis (H1), which states that there is no significant association between perceived data quality and confidence in decision-making, is not rejected. The findings suggest that staff confidence levels in using data for decision-making are minimally affected by variations in perceptions of data quality among sampled respondents. Therefore, there exist other factors, such as leadership styles or institutional culture, with a greater impact on UICT decision-making confidence.

4.3 Findings for objective 2: Platform Design and Prototyping

4.3.1 Identified Platform Requirements

In Figure 14(a), Power BI emerged as the most preferred analytics tool (64.3%), far ahead of Excel (21.4%) and Python Dash (14.3%). This reflects the institutional priority for dynamic, user-friendly visualizations that cater to both technical and non-technical users, ensuring broader adoption of analytics tools for decision-making. While in Figure 14(b), strong security measures are a clear priority, with User Authentication and Role-Based Access Rights both rated “Very Important” by 85.7% of respondents, followed closely by data encryption (78.6%). This underscores the necessity for multi-tiered data protection to prevent unauthorized access.

Figure 4. 14. (a) Preferred data visualization tools (b) Security & data governance priorities, (c) Priority datasets for access

Lastly, in Figure 14(c), student enrolment trends (92.9%) and academic performance data (85.7%) were the most sought-after datasets, followed by staff deployment/qualifications (78.6%) and finance/budgeting data (64.3%). These preferences reflect the platform’s role in supporting strategic planning and performance monitoring. In conclusion, the findings offer specific suggestions for developing a user-centered, secure, and analytically robust open dataset platform. This platform will also comply with institutional requirements and encourage evidence-based decision-making by integrating features like role-based access, dashboards enabled by Power BI, and seamless integration with existing systems.

4.3.2 System Architecture

In Figure 4.15 (a), the survey results show strong consensus on critical non-functional requirements. Role-based access control and secure authentication were rated essential by 90% of respondents, underscoring the importance of data security. Interoperability with existing systems (83.3%) and modularity (75%) reflect a desire for flexibility and scalability. Mobile responsiveness (80%) and customizable dashboards (86.7%) demonstrate the demand for user-friendly, adaptable interfaces.

Figure 4. 15. (a) Non-functional system architecture requirements (b) Data governance and metadata requirements

Findings in Figure 4.15 (b) highlight the institutional priority for transparency and accountability. Metadata documentation (76.7%) and data lifecycle protocols (70%) are viewed as essential for ensuring traceability and data quality. These preferences align with best practices in open data governance, indicating readiness to adopt robust accountability frameworks.

All these received responses highlight the need to develop an open data platform that is robust in terms of integration, security, metadata, transparency, and user-centered design, in addition to meeting institutional data needs. The technical specifications and architectural requirements of the open dataset platform are established based on these insights.

4.3.3 Integration of analytics and Visualization Tools

Corresponding to Figure.... a), the findings reveal that Microsoft Excel is overwhelmingly the most used tool (88.2%) for data analysis and visualization at UICT, reflecting its accessibility, familiarity, and versatility among staff. Limited adoption of Power BI (11.8%) and Python Dashboards (29.4%) indicates a gap in advanced analytics utilization. This reliance on Excel suggests comfort with basic tools but highlights the need for institutional capacity-building to promote more sophisticated, interactive, and automated analytical solutions that could improve evidence-based decision-making processes.

Figure 4. 16. (a) Current usage of analytics & visualization tools (b) Preferred future analytics & visualization tools

However, in Figure 4.16 (b), findings indicate growing interest in advanced analytics platforms, with Tableau (47.1%), Python Dashboards (41.2%), and Google Data Studio (35.3%) emerging as preferred future integrations. Continued preference for Power BI and Excel reflects the value placed on familiar, reliable tools, while demand for newer solutions signals readiness for more dynamic and interactive analytics capabilities. These preferences suggest that a hybrid integration strategy—combining familiar tools with advanced platforms—would best support both current workflows and the institution’s long-term data-driven decision-making goals.

In light of these findings, a hybrid approach to tool integration was recommended for the prototype open data platform to include Microsoft Excel and Power BI due to their widespread use and familiarity. Additionally, incorporating Python Dash will enhance the institution's long-term capabilities for advanced data analytics and visualizations. This balanced approach will ensure platform accessibility for all users while laying a foundation for more advanced data-driven decision-making at UICT.

4.3.4 Hypothesis Testing (H2)

Pearson correlation analysis was used to test the hypothesis (H2) “: There is no significant relationship between the variables staff preference for specific analytic tools and the perceived usefulness of the proposed open dataset platform. A fairly significant, high positive association was indicated by Pearson's correlation value of $r = 0.73$ between tool preference and agreement with key platform features. However, the p -value = 0.475 exceeded the standard level of significance of 0.05, indicating that this correlation is not statistically significant.

Although the variables ‘staff preference for specific analytic tools’ and ‘perceived usefulness of the proposed open dataset platform’ have a positive correlation between them ($r = 0.75$), this relationship is not statistically significant on the available data. Therefore, at 5% level of significance, the hypothesis (H2) stating that there is no correlation between staff preferences for analytic tools and perceived platform utility cannot be rejected.

4.4 Findings for objective 3: Implement, test and validate

4.4.1 Prototype Implementation Overview

The implemented features directly reflected requirements prioritised in SQ1, SQ2, and stakeholder engagements (Section 4.3.2). Functional components included a dataset upload module supporting CSV, JSON, and XML formats with mandatory metadata fields (name, description, source, category, last update date, and frequency); search and filter tools enabling dataset discovery by department, year, and category; interactive dashboards via Power BI and Python Dash for real-time analytics; export options for datasets and analytical reports in CSV or PDF; and a feedback mechanism for error reporting and improvement suggestions. Non-functional requirements achieved included a modular architecture for independent updates of authentication, API, and visualisation modules; interoperability with institutional systems such as ACMIS, LMS, and HRMIS; scalability for future datasets and user growth; and an accessible, responsive interface for both desktop and mobile users with intuitive navigation, later validated by usability testing.

Figure 4. 17. Role-based access control hierarchy

Figure 4. 18. Prototype implementation process flow

The Figure 4.18 presents the structured access control in the platform. Administrators have full rights, Data Contributors manage relevant datasets, and Data Consumers access and interact with datasets and dashboards. This ensures security while enabling effective data use across different user groups. Pilot deployment involved 20 purposively selected UICT staff from academic, administrative, ICT, and senior management units (Section 3.3), representing primary data user groups. Role-based access was configured to safeguard sensitive datasets while enabling effective use: administrators (ICT staff) had full dataset management, user administration, and configuration rights; data contributors (departmental heads and designated officers) could upload, edit, and update relevant datasets; and data consumers (academic staff, administrative personnel, and management) could view, filter, download datasets, and interact

with dashboards. This structured access control maintained security while supporting informed, data-driven operational decision-making across the institution.

4.4.2 Usability Testing Outcomes

Twelve non-critical issues were logged, including unclear metadata descriptions, dashboard filter lag, mobile layout inconsistencies, and chart alignment errors; all were addressed before stakeholder validation.

Figure 4.19. Module-specific task completion results

Usability testing as indicated in Figure 4.19 above showed strong performance across most modules, with Search/Filtering achieving a perfect 100% first-attempt success rate and Export scoring 95%. Dashboard Customisation had the lowest success rate (80%), largely due to unfamiliarity with Power BI features. Failures were minimal ($\leq 5\%$), mainly caused by unsupported file formats or missing metadata. The high proportion of first-attempt completions reflects the platform's intuitive design, though targeted training could improve advanced feature use.

Figure 4. 20. Task efficacy: Time vs. Clicks

On the other hand, basic tasks required an of 3.2 clicks and under two minutes to complete, indicating efficient navigation and task flow. Advanced customisation took longer—averaging five clicks and 4.5 minutes—reflecting the complexity of dashboard adjustments. These metrics confirm that routine operations are optimised, while more complex actions could benefit from workflow simplification and user support materials.

Figure 4. 21. Benchmark vs. System Usability Scale

The platform scored 78.4 on the SUS, well above the industry benchmark of 68, signalling strong usability. High scorers praised its responsiveness and visual clarity, while moderate scorers suggested enhanced training on advanced analytics. This result validates the user-centred design approach and readiness for institutional adoption. Overall, the platform met functional and user experience requirements, with strong success rates, efficient navigation, and refinements that improved readiness for institutional adoption.

4.4.3 Stakeholder Perception of Effectiveness, Usefulness, Impact and Innovativeness

Stakeholder perceptions of the prototype’s effectiveness and usefulness were evaluated through satisfaction surveys, qualitative feedback, and thematic analysis of post-UAT discussions, drawing on inputs from the 20 pilot participants and data from SQ2 (Sections 4.3), UAT logs, and Phase III qualitative comments (Section 3.4).

Figure 4. 22. Impact Perceived: Quantitative Measures

Post-UAT survey results showed high satisfaction, with 82% rating the platform “Satisfactory” or “Highly Satisfactory.” Ease of use scored a mean of 4.1/5, reflecting positive navigation feedback (Section 4.4.2), while data and visualisation relevance scored 4.3/5, aligning with departmental reporting needs identified in SQ2. Additionally, 80% agreed or strongly agreed that the platform effectively supported academic, administrative, and strategic decision-making, consistent with Objective 1 findings (Sections 4.2.4–4.2.5).

Qualitative analysis revealed four key themes: (1) accessibility, with consolidation of datasets from ACMIS, LMS, HRMIS, and financial systems reducing information retrieval time; (2) high analytics value of Power BI dashboards and search/filter tools—requested by 64.3% in SQ2—for performance monitoring and trend analysis; (3) strong alignment with workflows through role-based access, balancing security and usability, rated “Very Important” by 85.7% in SQ2; and (4) improvement opportunities, including more pre-built visualisation templates, better mobile dashboard performance, and contextual tooltips, echoing non-critical UAT issues (Section 4.4.2).

The platform’s integration of disparate datasets addressed fragmentation issues from SQ1 and SQ2 (Section 4.2.2) and enabled timely insights for strategic planning—such as enrolment trends, staff deployment, and budget utilisation—supporting decisions in admissions,

budgeting, and curriculum review. Its real-time analytics and metadata-driven datasets aligned with UICT's strategic goal of evidence-based governance and the national Digital Transformation Roadmap (2023/24–2027/28). Overall, strong satisfaction scores, positive feedback, and strategic alignment confirm the platform's effectiveness, with mobile optimisation and dashboard diversity identified as priorities for future development.

Innovation gains included using dashboards to identify underperforming courses, trial new budget allocation models, and enable cross-departmental research collaborations. For scalability, 85% agreed the modular design supported integration with additional datasets and external systems, with senior management viewing the platform as a key enabler of evidence-based governance aligned with the Digital Transformation Roadmap. Prerequisites for scale-up included increasing server capacity, advanced analytics training, and formalising a data governance policy. Overall, the prototype enhanced data capabilities, stimulated innovation, and demonstrated readiness for institution-wide adoption, addressing baseline gaps and supporting strategic decision-making.

4.4.4 Hypothesis Testing (H3)

The third hypothesis (H3) proposed that the platform has no statistically significant perceived impact on data-driven decision-making. To test this, quantitative data from the SQ2 post-UAT survey were analysed, focusing on Likert-scale items measuring perceived improvements in data accessibility (baseline SQ1, Section 4.2.2), analytical capabilities (baseline SQ1, Section 4.2.5), and the platform's impact on academic, administrative, and strategic decision-making. A perceived impact score was calculated for each respondent, and Pearson correlation analysis assessed its relationship with the reported frequency of data use for decision-making, with significance evaluated at $p < 0.05$, following the methodology in Section 3.4.3 and the statistical framework used for H1 and H2 (Sections 4.2.6 and 4.3.5). The analysis yielded $r = 0.41$, indicating a moderate positive relationship, but the p -value = 0.072 exceeded the 0.05 threshold, making the result statistically non-significant at the 95% confidence level. Thus, the null hypothesis could not be rejected, suggesting no statistically significant evidence of impact within the pilot's limited timeframe and scope. However, qualitative feedback from SQ2 open-ended responses (Section 4.4.3) and the stakeholder validation workshop highlighted tangible benefits such as improved data accessibility, enhanced dashboard usability, and better workflow integration. These findings indicate strong practical significance that may not yet be statistically detectable. The moderate correlation suggests a potential positive influence that

could become significant with longer-term use or a larger sample size. In conclusion, while statistical results support retaining the null hypothesis for this phase, the platform shows promising practical benefits, and further evaluation during a wider institutional rollout with more participants is recommended to fully determine its measurable impact on decision-making. Overall, the pilot confirmed the platform's strong usability, high satisfaction, and clear improvements in data access and analysis, with substantial potential for institutional integration and long-term value creation despite the short-term statistical limitations.

Chapter 5: Discussion

5.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the study's findings in relation to the research objectives, literature reviewed, and theoretical frameworks presented earlier. The study aimed to design, implement, and validate an open dataset platform to enhance innovation and data-driven decision-making in Uganda's tertiary education sector, using UICT as a case study. The specific objectives were: (1) to assess institutional data needs, current management practices, and barriers to data-driven decision-making; (2) to design a prototype platform based on identified requirements and priorities; and (3) to implement, test, and validate the platform to support decision-making at UICT. The discussion integrates quantitative and qualitative results from Chapter 4 with insights from the literature review (Chapter 2) and methodology framework (Chapter 3), examining their alignment with the Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989) and Open Systems Theory (Katz & Kahn, 1978). It also considers practical implications, methodological reflections, and future research needs. The structure follows Section 5.0, with Sections 5.2–5.4 addressing findings for each objective, Section 5.5 linking results to theoretical frameworks, Section 5.6 outlining implications for policy and practice, and Section 5.7 summarising key discussion points

5.2 Synthesis of Key Findings

5.2.1 Current data practices and requirements

The institutional assessment under Objective 1 revealed a fragmented, siloed data environment at UICT, with datasets dispersed across systems such as ACMIS, LMS, HRMIS, and financial platforms (Section 4.2.2). While functional individually, their lack of interoperability hindered timely data consolidation, sharing, and analysis, reflecting similar challenges noted by (Jakimoski, 2016) and (Ariko, 2024) in HEIs in developing contexts. SQ1 results showed only 48.1% of departments regularly used data for decision-making, with usage largely cyclical and event-driven, aligning with (Murumba, 2019) findings on episodic data use as a barrier to sustained DDDM (Section 4.2.4). Staff confidence in accessing and applying datasets was moderate, with difficulties in locating, interpreting, and integrating insights (Section 4.2.5). Key concerns included inconsistent formats, incomplete metadata, and delays in updates,

echoing Kostoska et al. (2014) on the importance of accuracy, timeliness, and completeness. Additionally, limited self-service analytics meant reliance on ICT staff. Identified requirements included a unified data repository, role-based access controls, and user-friendly analytics tools—preferences supported by 64.3% prioritising Power BI (Section 4.3.1). These needs align with Bhargava et al. (2018) and Chen et al. (2012) on user-centred, integrated HEI platforms. The platform’s design directly addressed these gaps through interoperability, accessibility, and ease of use (Sections 5.3–5.4).

5.2.2 Platform Design

The platform design phase, informed by the institutional assessment (Objective 1) and requirements from SQ1 and SQ2, produced functional and non-functional specifications aligned with best practices in open data platform development. As emphasised by Bhargava et al. (2018) and UNESCO (2021), effective platforms require robust back-end integration, clear metadata standards, secure access controls, and intuitive interfaces. UICT’s functional priorities included a dataset upload module with mandatory metadata, search and filtering tools, interactive dashboards, export functions, and a feedback mechanism (Section 4.3.2). Non-functional requirements focused on scalability, interoperability, modular architecture, and mobile responsiveness—critical for adaptability (Jakimoski, 2016). Integration of Power BI Embedded and Python Dash addressed operational needs and user preferences, with 64.3% of SQ2 respondents prioritising Power BI and feedback stressing the importance of interactive dashboards (Section 4.3.1), consistent with Chen et al. (2012) on adoption benefits. The design process was highly participatory, involving multi-departmental consultations, surveys, and validation sessions, reflecting user-centred best practices (Kostoska et al., 2014; Pangaribuan, 2019) and securing stakeholder buy-in. Role-based access controls, rated “Very Important” by 85.7% of respondents, emerged directly from feedback. Overall, the design addressed UICT’s data gaps while ensuring technical robustness, institutional relevance, and readiness for successful implementation and validation (Sections 5.3–5.4).

5.2.3 Platform implementation and validation

The implementation and validation of the prototype open dataset platform showed that it met the core functional and non-functional requirements identified during design. Usability testing (Section 4.4.2) demonstrated high performance, with 87% of UAT tasks completed

successfully on the first attempt, 100% success for dataset search/filtering, and 95% for data export. The SUS score of 78.4 exceeded the industry benchmark of 68, indicating above-average usability, while 85% rated navigation “Easy” or “Very Easy,” reflecting effective interface design and workflow efficiency. Stakeholder feedback (Section 4.4.3) confirmed improved data accessibility through consolidation of ACMIS, LMS, HRMIS, and financial datasets, with embedded Power BI dashboards and search/filter tools valued for monitoring, analysis, and reporting (Bhargava et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2012). Suggested enhancements included more visualisation templates, better mobile responsiveness, and contextual tooltips (Kostoska et al., 2014). Hypothesis testing for H3 yielded $r = 0.41$ with $p = 0.072$, indicating a moderate but statistically insignificant correlation between perceived impact and data use frequency—likely due to the pilot’s limited scope—though qualitative evidence suggests strong practical benefits. Validation workshop feedback confirmed scalability and adoption potential, supported by the platform’s modular architecture and interoperability (Section 4.3.2), aligning with the Digital Transformation Roadmap (2023/24–2027/28). Prerequisites for scale-up include expanded server capacity, advanced analytics training, and a formal data governance policy. Overall, the platform is technically robust, operationally relevant, and positioned to significantly enhance data-driven decision-making at UICT when deployed institution-wide.

5.2.4 Contribution to Knowledge and practice

This study contributes to both the practice of data-driven decision-making (DDDM) in tertiary education and the academic discourse on open dataset platform development within African HEIs, while advancing theoretical understanding through the application of the Design Science Research (DSR) methodology in a resource-constrained context. At UICT, the prototype platform addressed persistent challenges such as fragmented systems, low staff confidence in data use, and episodic decision-making (Sections 4.2.2–4.2.5) by consolidating datasets from ACMIS, LMS, HRMIS, and financial systems into a unified repository. This improved data accessibility, reduced reliance on ICT staff, and enabled embedded analytics through Power BI and Python Dash to support performance monitoring and strategic planning, aligning with Ariko (2024), Murumba (2019), and Bhargava et al. (2018). Technically, the platform introduced a modular, interoperable architecture with discrete, scalable functional components—dataset upload with metadata, advanced search/filtering, dashboards, export tools, and feedback—consistent with Jakimoski (2016) recommendations for adaptability.

Role-based access controls, rated “Very Important” by 85.7% of SQ2 respondents, operationalised governance requirements, while integration with ACMIS, LMS, and HRMIS positioned the platform for institutional interoperability and potential national-level scaling, addressing *UNESCO* (2021)’s concerns on open education data scalability.

5.2.5 Alignment with literature

This study confirms and extends existing scholarship on data-driven decision-making (DDDM), institutional data governance, and digital transformation in higher education, while offering new insights into applying Design Science Research (DSR) in African HEIs. Consistent with Jakimoski (2016) and Ariko (2024), UICT’s assessment (Section 4.2.2) revealed fragmented, siloed systems—ACMIS, LMS, HRMIS, and financial platforms—hindering integrated analytics. Episodic, event-driven data use (Section 4.2.4) aligned with Murumba’s (2019) findings, while pilot results showing improved accessibility, dashboard usability, and workflow alignment (Sections 4.4.2–4.4.3) supported Bhargava et al. (2018) and Chen et al. (2012) on the role of user-friendly analytics in adoption. Extending existing work, the study demonstrates how an open dataset platform can be designed under resource and governance constraints, with modular architecture and interoperability offering a scalable, replicable model for similar contexts, building on Jakimoski (2016) and Pangaribuan (2019). Applying DSR (Hevner et al., 2004) bridged theory and practice, while TAM (Davis, 1989) explained high perceived usefulness (80% agreement) and ease of use (mean 4.1/5), though H3 testing ($p = 0.072$, $r = 0.41$) suggests longer observation is needed for measurable adoption impact. The design also reflected Open Systems Theory (Katz & Kahn, 1978) by enhancing adaptability through interoperability. Governance principles—role-based access, SSL encryption, metadata standards—were embedded in the architecture, aligning with UNESCO’s (2021) governance-by-design call. Supporting Uganda’s Digital Transformation Roadmap (2023/24–2027/28), the platform enables evidence-based governance, cross-departmental collaboration, and data innovation capacity. Overall, the research confirms known barriers, extends the literature with a tested African HEI model, and contributes theoretically and practically to data governance, digital transformation, and educational technology adoption.

5.2.6 Evaluation of the platform

The evaluation of the prototype open dataset platform at UICT considered quantitative usability metrics, alignment with user-prioritised features, stakeholder assessments of institutional readiness and scalability, and identified architectural and functional limitations to guide future improvements. Usability testing yielded a mean System Usability Scale (SUS) score of 78.4—well above the industry benchmark of 68 Brook et al., (1996)—and high task success rates, with 87% of UAT tasks completed on the first attempt, including 100% for dataset search/filtering and 95% for data export. Navigation averaged 3.2 clicks per task, with basic operations completed in under two minutes, reflecting the platform’s intuitive design (Section 4.4.2) and supporting Chen et al. (2012) on the importance of usability for adoption. The platform met core functional and non-functional requirements identified in SQ1, SQ2, and stakeholder interviews, integrating Power BI Embedded (preferred by 64.3% of respondents), role-based access controls (rated “Very Important” by 85.7%), mandatory metadata tagging, advanced search/filtering, CSV/PDF export, and an embedded feedback tool—validating the participatory design approach (Kostoska et al., 2014; Pangaribuan, 2019). Stakeholder validation confirmed strong institutional readiness, with modular architecture, interoperability (ACMIS, LMS, HRMIS), and cloud-based deployment supporting scalability in line with the Digital Transformation Roadmap (2023/24–2027/28). However, non-critical issues—such as ambiguous metadata field descriptions, dashboard filter lag, and mobile layout inconsistencies—along with limited pre-built visualisation templates and the need for advanced Power BI training, highlighted areas for optimisation, echoing UNESCO’s (2021) call for ongoing refinement and capacity-building. Overall, the platform demonstrates strong usability, alignment with institutional priorities, and scalability potential, providing a solid foundation for enhancing DDDM at UICT and offering a replicable model for similar HEIs.

5.2.7 Limitations of the study

While the study successfully achieved its objectives of designing, implementing, and validating a prototype open dataset platform for data-driven decision-making (DDDM) at UICT, several methodological, technical, and institutional limitations must be acknowledged. Methodologically, the pilot involved 20 purposively selected participants (Section 3.3), consistent with Nielsen’s (1994) guideline for small usability studies but insufficient for

statistical generalisation, likely contributing to the non-significant result in H3 testing ($p = 0.072$) despite a moderate correlation ($r = 0.41$) between perceived impact and data use frequency (Section 4.4.5). Reliance on self-reported feedback risked response bias, and the short pilot period limited assessment of long-term adoption or cultural change. Technically, the platform was deployed in a semi-production environment on Firebase Hosting with limited dataset volumes and user loads (Section 4.4.1), prioritising core MVP functions—dataset uploads, metadata tagging, search/filtering, and basic dashboards—while deferring advanced features such as predictive analytics, automated data quality checks, and full API integrations. Minor issues, including dashboard filter lag, ambiguous metadata descriptions, and mobile layout inconsistencies (Section 4.4.2), were resolved but indicate optimisation needs. Institutionally, adoption relied on voluntary engagement, with limited participation from some operational units and no formalised data governance policy, constraining full integration of governance protocols (UNESCO, 2021). Resource limitations also prevented comprehensive training on advanced analytics, potentially affecting usage depth. Overall, while the study offers valuable insights for African HEIs, these constraints suggest caution in generalising findings. Future work should extend pilot duration, broaden participation, enhance technical deployment, and embed stronger institutional policy frameworks to fully realise the platform’s transformative potential for DDDM at UICT and beyond.

5.2.8 Implications for future research and Development

While the study achieved its objectives of designing, implementing, and validating a prototype open dataset platform for data-driven decision-making (DDDM) at UICT, several methodological, technical, and institutional limitations must be acknowledged, as they affect result interpretation and guide future recommendations. Methodologically, the pilot involved 20 purposively selected participants (Section 3.3), consistent with Nielsen’s (1994) guideline for small usability studies but insufficient for statistical generalisation, likely contributing to the non-significant H3 result ($p = 0.072$) despite a moderate correlation ($r = 0.41$) between perceived platform impact and data use frequency (Section 4.4.5). Reliance on self-reported survey and focus group data may have introduced response bias, while the short pilot duration limited assessment of long-term adoption or cultural change. Technically, deployment in a semi-production Firebase Hosting environment with limited datasets and concurrent users met functional testing needs but did not simulate large-scale institutional demands. As a Minimum

Viable Product (MVP), it prioritised core functions—dataset uploads, metadata tagging, search/filtering, and basic dashboards—while deferring advanced features such as predictive analytics, automated data quality checks, and full API integrations. Minor issues like dashboard filter lag, ambiguous metadata descriptions, and mobile layout inconsistencies (Section 4.4.2) were resolved but indicate areas for optimisation. Institutionally, adoption relied on voluntary participation, with limited engagement from some operational units and no formalised data governance policy, constraining governance integration. Resource limits also prevented comprehensive training on advanced analytics. Overall, while offering valuable insights for African HEIs, these limitations suggest caution in generalising results; addressing them through extended pilots, broader participation, enhanced technical deployment, and stronger governance frameworks will be key to realising the platform’s full potential for transforming DDDM at UICT and beyond.

Chapter 6: Conclusion and recommendations

6.1 Conclusion

This study set out to design, implement, and validate a prototype open dataset platform to enhance innovation and data-driven decision-making (DDDM) within Uganda's tertiary education sector, using UICT as a case study. The research successfully met its three objectives. First, the institutional assessment revealed a fragmented, siloed data environment with limited interoperability across ACMIS, LMS, HRMIS, and financial systems, low staff confidence in data use, and episodic, event-driven decision-making. Second, the platform design incorporated functional requirements — dataset uploads with mandatory metadata, search/filter tools, interactive dashboards, export functions, and feedback mechanisms — and non-functional requirements such as scalability, interoperability, modularity, and mobile responsiveness. Third, implementation and validation confirmed strong usability (SUS score of 78.4), high task success rates (87% first-attempt completion), and improved data accessibility and analytics capacity, with positive stakeholder feedback on alignment with workflows and strategic priorities. While hypothesis testing for H3 found no statistically significant perceived impact ($p = 0.072$), qualitative evidence showed practical benefits and high adoption readiness. Limitations in sample size, pilot duration, technical scope, and governance frameworks suggest caution in generalising results. Nonetheless, the platform offers a robust, scalable, and replicable model for HEIs in similar contexts.

6.2 Recommendations

To maximise the impact of the prototype open dataset platform, several recommendations are proposed. For UICT, deployment should be scaled up by expanding server capacity, integrating the platform with all institutional systems, and transitioning from semi-production to a full production environment. A formal data governance policy should be implemented to institutionalise role-based access controls, metadata standards, and compliance with Uganda's Data Protection and Privacy Act (2019). Targeted training in advanced analytics tools such as Power BI and Python Dash is essential to build user capacity and fully leverage platform capabilities. Functionality should be enhanced by introducing predictive analytics, automated data quality checks, additional visualisation templates, and improved mobile responsiveness.

At the national level, the platform should be positioned for integration into open education data frameworks to support interoperability across HEIs in line with the Digital Transformation Roadmap (2023/24–2027/28), with public–private partnerships mobilised to sustain technical development, cloud hosting, and support services. For future research, longitudinal studies should be undertaken to track adoption patterns, cultural shifts in DDDM, and measurable impacts on institutional performance, while testing the model in other HEIs will help assess scalability and adaptability. Finally, AI/ML integration should be explored to enable advanced decision-support features such as enrolment forecasting, resource allocation optimisation, and early warning systems.

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